

Infographic #5: Understanding Wavelength in Neuroimaging

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Understanding Wavelength in Neuroimaging

A guide to Frequency, amplitude, and sampling in neuroimaging signals.

ACN 6375 | CHERRENDER BROWN

INTRODUCTION: IDENTIFYING WAVE CHARACTERISTICS

Crest: B B F

Troughs: D B H

Wavelength (λ): EX: B to F

Amplitude: X-axis to F

Oscillation: A to E

FREQUENCY

Definition:
The property or condition occurring at frequent intervals.
The number of times an event occurs within a given period.

Explanation:

- Recurrence rate.
- Number of cycles per second.
- The unit of Frequency is Hertz [Hz].

Key Points:

- Amplitude is the size of the signal
- Oscillation is the movement between points

High Frequency wave

Low Frequency wave

WAVELENGTH FORMULA

$$\lambda = \frac{v}{f}$$

λ = wavelength [meters]
v = velocity [m/s]
f = Frequency [Hz]

20 waves in 1 second: 20Hz
F = 20Hz

1 wave is 1/20th of a second
T = .05sec

Sample of waves in neuroimaging

EEG showing typical brain waves of sleep and wakefulness [relaxed state]

Neurophysiological Monitoring during Intradural Spinal Tumor Surgery [Iltan et al. 2024]

Quick Quiz!

1. Which wave has the largest λ?
2. Which wave has the highest F?
3. Which wave has the highest amplitude?
4. Which waves have the same λ?

1:B ; 2:D ; 3:A ; 4:BC